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XALQARO MUNOSABATLARDA TRANSCHEGARAVIY DARYOLAR MUAMMOLARINI HAL ETISH YECHIMLARI

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ANNOTATSIYA

Transchegaraviy daryolarni boshqarish xalqaro munosabatlar tizimida judda katta ahamiyatga ega hisoblanadi. Iqlim o'zgarishi va institutsional kamchiliklar muammolarni yanada murakkablashtirmoqda. Diplomatik vositalar, xalqaro tashkilotlar va uchinchi tomon ishtiroki muhim bo'lsa-da, ularning aralashuvi har doim ham samarali natija bermasligi mumkin. Ushbu maqolada shu va shunga o'xshash fikrlar haqida mulohaza yuritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: *Kuch asimmetriyasi, Transchegaraviy daryo, Daryo havzasi tashkiloti, "to'lqin ta'siri", Mekong, Gang.*

SOLUTIONS TO TRANSBOUNDARY RIVER ISSUES IN INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

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ABSTRACT

The management of transboundary rivers holds significant importance in the international relations system. Climate change and institutional shortcomings further complicate these issues. While diplomatic instruments, international organizations, and third-party involvement play a crucial role, their intervention does not always lead to effective outcomes. This article explores these and similar considerations.

Key words: *Power asymmetry, transboundary river, river basin organization, "ripple effect," Mekong, Ganges.*

KIRISH

Bugungi shiddat bilan rivojlanayotgan texnologiya zamonida suv energiya, qishloq xo'jaligi, aholi salomatligi, transportning ajralmas bir qismiga aylanib qolgan.

Hozirgi kunda suv manbalari bilan bog'liq inqirozning ahamiyati global miqyosda oshib bormoqda. Bu ayniqsa ikki yoki undan ortiq davlat hududidan oqib o'tuvchi daryolarda ya'ni transchegaraviy daryolarda yaqqol ko'rinmoqda. Shu vaqtgacha transchegaraviy daryolar global siyosatda markaziy, ammo kam e'tibor beriladigan masala hisoblanar edi¹. Birlashgan Millatlar Tashkilotining ma'lumotlariga qaraganda umumiy hisobda 148 davlat hudida ikki yoki undan ortiq mamlakat siyosiy chegaralarini o'z ichiga oluvchi xalqaro daryo havzalari joylashgan². Ushbu daryolar yer sharining quruqlik maydonini 46 foizini o'z ichiga oladi va dunyo aholisining deyarli 40 foiz qismini suv manbasi bilan ta'minlaydi va xalqaro daryo oqimining 60 foizini ni tashkil qiladi.³

ADABIYOTLAR TAHLILI VA METODOLOGIYASI

Manbalarning birinchi guruhini xalqaro suvlarni tartibga solish bo'yicha xalqaro tashkilotlar hujjatlari, BMTning atrof-muhit bo'yicha tahliliy hujjatlari, CAREC, ICWC hisobotlari va ma'lumotlar to'plamlari kiradi. Alohida ta'kidlab o'tish joizki, Xalqaro suv oqimlaridan navigatsiyasiz foydalanish huquqi to'g'risidagi konventsiya. Transchegaraviy suv oqimlari va xalqaro ko'llarni muhofaza qilish va ulardan foydalanish to'g'risidagi konventsiya, suv resurslari to'g'risidagi Berlin qoidalari, Xalqaro daryolar suvlaridan foydalanish bo'yicha Xelsinki qoidalari va suv muammolarini tartibga solish va hal qilish uchun xalqaro me'yoriy-huquqiy baza bo'lgan bir qator boshqa hujjatlar.

MUHOKAMA

Suv manbalari bilan bog'liq muammolarni hal qilishda dunyoda yagona umumiy yechim turi mavjud emas, bu muammoning qaysi mintaqada yuz

¹ Wolf, Aaron T., Shira B. Yoffe and Mark Giordano. "International Waters: Indicators for Identifying Basins at Risk." Water Policy 2003. 5: 29-p http://www.cawater-info.net/bk/water_law/pdf/pccp_20_international_waters_e.pdf

² UN Water. 2016. "Statistics." Accessed March 18, 2016. <http://www.unwater.org/statistics/en>

³ Wolf, Aaron T., Shira B. Yoffe and Mark Giordano. "International Waters: Indicators for Identifying Basins at Risk." Water Policy 2003 5: 33. http://www.cawater-info.net/bk/water_law/pdf/pccp_20_international_waters_e.pdf

berayotganligi va o'sha mintaqa yoki davlatda suvga bo'lgan talab qaysi darajada ekanligiga bog'liq albatta¹. Xalqaro tinchlik va taraqqiyot uchun katta ahamiyatga ega bo'lishiga qaramasdan, transchegaraviy daryolarni boshqarish bo'yicha mavjud bilimlar yetarli emas². Bundan tashqari, Xalqaro daryolarni boshqarish bo'yicha mavjud institutlar chuchuk suvga bo'lgan talabning ortishi va takliflarning kamayishi yoki beqarorligi sababli yetarli bo'lmayapdi. Muammoga qo'shimcha ravishda, iqlim o'zgarishi tahdidi mavjud suvni taqsimlash va xalqaro daryolarni boshqarish rejimlari hamda institutlarini imkoniyatlarini kamaytra boshladi³.

Mamlakatlarning tashqi siyosatida transchegaraviy daryolar bilan bog'liq muammolar asosiy o'rnida turishi kerak, buning asosiy sababi transchegaraviy daryolarni boshqarishning siyosiy xarakteri mojarolarni oldini olish, mintaqaviy olish, mintaqaviy barqarorlik, ekologik tinchlik va xavfsizlik masalalarida ahamiyati katta.

Transchegaraviy daryolarning boshqaruvi ko'pincha havza siyosati bilan qamrab olinadi va bu siyosat, o'z navbatida, ko'pincha kuch asimmetriyasi bilan murakkablashdi⁴. Bizga ma'lumki Kuch asimmetriyasi - bu davlatlar yoki boshqa ishtirokchilar o'rtasida iqtisodiy, siyosiy, harbiy, yoki texnik imkoniyatlar bo'yicha mavjud bo'lgan nomutanosiblikni anglatadi. Kuch asimmetriyasi ko'pincha muzokaralar jarayoniga, qaror qabul qilishga va resurslardan foydalanish imkoniyatlariga ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Bu esa o'z navbatida suv muammolari bilan shug'ullanadigan mutaxassislar uchun qiyinchilik tug'diradi.

Dunyo bo'yicha transchegaraviy daryolarning yarmidan kamrog'ida ulardan foydalanish bo'yicha rasmiy kelishuv shartnomalari mavjud⁵. Bundan tashqari, suv

¹ Swain, Ashok. "Managing Water Conflict: Asia, Africa and the Middle East". London: Routledge 2004. 11-p. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/287341421_Managing_Water_Conflict_Asia_Africa_and_the_Middle_East

² Earle, Anton., Jägerskog, A. and Öjendal, A., eds. "Transboundary Water Management: Principles and Practice". London: Earthscan. 2010. 53-p. https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Anton-Earle/publication/262916630_Transboundary_Water_Management_Principles_and_Practice/links/57d29c9808ae5f03b48cac9c/Transboundary-Water-Management-Principles-and-Practice.pdf

³ Gleick, Peter, ed.. The World's Water 2008–2009. London: Island Press. 2009. https://islandpress.org/books/worlds-water-2008-2009?gad_source=1&gclid=CjwKCAiAnpy9BhAkEiwA-P8N4qk5w13Pk33ihKbgmbhfUL8wJCu2FErKZYqQPzX8yp0suOVOkmEnERoCQ54QAuD_BwE#desc

⁴ M.Zeitoun, J.Warner. "Hydro-hegemony—A Framework for Analysis of Trans-Boundary Water Conflicts." Water Policy 8: 2006. P-435. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/40112175_Hydro-Hegemony-a_Framework_for_Analysis_of_Trans-Boundary_Water_Conflicts

⁵ G.Mark, A.Drieschova, J.A.Duncan, Y.Sayama, L.Stefano, T.A.Wolf. "A Review of the Evolution and State of Transboundary Freshwater Treaties." International Environmental Agreements: Politics, Law and Economics 13: 3. 2013.

havzalari bo'yicha institutsionallashtirilgan hamkorliklar soni juda ham kam hisoblanadi: 276 ta transchegaraviy daryo havzasidan atigi 116 tasida daryo havzasini boshqarish tashkiloti (River Basin Organization, RBO) faoliyat yurutadi¹. Shu bilan birga faqat shartnomalarning o'zi muammoning yechimi bo'la olmaydi va ular nizolarga barham bera olmasligi mumkin.

Ma'lumotlarga qaraganda hozirgi kunga qadar hali biron marta "suv urushlari" yuz bermagan². Ammo suv resurslarini noto'g'ri boshqarish va ijtimoiy-siyosiy beqarorlik o'rtasida bog'liqlik mavjud va bu xavflar iqlim o'zgarishi natijasida yanada kuchayishi mumkin. Bunday xavflarning yaqqol misollari sifatida, Suriyadagi fuqarolar urushiga olib kelgan voqealar, Pokistonda toshqin va qurg'oqchilik oqibatlarini keltirishimiz mumkin³.

Bu kabi beqarorliklar nafaqat davlatlararo ziddiyatlarni, balki davlat ichidagi, keyinchalik xalqaro tus olishi mumkin bo'lgan nizolarni ham keltirib chiqarishi mumkin. Shunday sharoitda, transchegaraviy suv boshqaruvi bo'yicha tashqi siyosiy ishtirok nizoli suv masalalarini hal qilishda qo'l kelishi mumkin. Ba'zi hollarda esa, suv muammosi siyosiy tus olgan taqdirda uchunchi tomoning aralashuvi ham samarli bo'lishi mumkin. Shu bilan birga suv muammolari "ko'prik resursi" bo'lishi mumkin, ya'ni suv diplomatiyasi orqali boshqa muammolarga ham yechim topilishi mumkin. Bu esa mintaqaviy tinchlik va hamkorlik nuqtai nazaridan ijobiy natijalarga erishish uchun vosita bo'lib xizmat qilishi mumkin. Suv bo'yicha hamkorlik davlatlar o'rtasida ishonchsizlik va shubhalarini o'zgartirib, umumiy manfaatlarga erishish imkoniyatini yaratishi va o'zaro manfaatdorlik modelini shakillantirishi ehtimoli

P-17.

<https://transboundarywaters.ceoas.oregonstate.edu/sites/transboundarywaters.ceoas.oregonstate.edu/files/Publications/Giordano%20et%20al.%20Treaty%20Update%204-13.pdf>

¹ S.Susanne. "Governing International Watercourses: River Basin Organizations and the Sustainable Governance of Internationally Shared Rivers and Lakes". New York: Routledge, 2013. P-211. https://www.routledge.com/Governing-International-Watercourses-River-Basin-Organizations-and-the-Sustainable-Governance-of-Internationally-Shared-Rivers-and-Lakes/Schmeier/p/book/9781138900509?srsId=AfmBOopZzT23o1dAtTpTizp7--tUji5S_9RN3-9y6DPI7xg4MEOTBqHb

² T.A.Wolf, S.B.Yoffe, M.Giordano. "International Waters: Indicators for Identifying Basins at Risk." Water Policy 5: 29. 2003. P-56.

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/313656395_International_waters_Indicators_for_identifying_basins_at_risk

³ G.H.Peter. "Water, Drought, Climate Change, and Conflict in Syria." Weather, Climate & Society 6: 331. 2014. P-335. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/274576248_Water_Drought_Climate_Change_and_Conflict_in_Syria

mavjud. Bu shuningdek yanada katta o‘zaro bog‘liqlik va jamiyatlararo aloqalarning rivojlanishiga yo‘l ochadi. Suv resurslari bo‘yicha ikki tomonlama hamkorlikning boshqa sohalarga ham tarqalishi kam uchraydigan hodisa emas¹.

XULOSA

Suv manbalari bilan bog‘liq hamkorlik osonlik bilan vujudga kelmaydi va to‘g‘ridan-to‘g‘ri tinchlikni mustahkamlash ta‘siriga ega bo‘lmaydi. Konka va Dabelko tabiiy resurslar, jumladan suv manbalari ustidan hamkorlik uchun kuchli asoslarni o‘z asarlarida keltirishgan². Ular suv resurslari bo‘yicha tinchlik o‘rnatishni ikki yo‘nalishini ko‘rsatishgan.

Bundan tashqari, hukumatlararo hamkorlik to‘g‘risidagi xalqaro kelishuvga erishiladigan muvaffaqiyatli tashqi siyosiy ishtirok ham yetarli bo‘lmasligi mumkin, chunki bu xalqaro bitimlar tufayli manfaatlari hisobga olinmagan ijtimoiy guruhlar tomonidan qarshilikka sabab bo‘lishi ehtimoli mavjud³.

Ammo texnik kelishuvlarni siyosiy jihatdan qo‘llab-quvvatlash muammoni yechishda katta ijobiy o‘zgarishlarga olib kelishi va mintaqaviy tinchlik va hamkorlikni rivojlantirishga hissa qo‘shishi mumkin.

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¹ K.Conca, D.G.Dabelko. “Environmental Peacemaking. Baltimore”. Johns Hopkins University Press. 2002. P-17. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/280720918_Environmental_Peacemaking

² Ibid. P-33.

³ K.Conca. “Decoupling Water and Violent Conflict.” *Issues in Science and Technology* 29: 39. 2012. P-41. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/280796520_Decoupling_Water_and_Violent_Conflict

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